

This document is a working chronostratigraphic synthesis compiled for personal research purposes. It integrates data from primary literature across stratigraphy, geochronology, palaeoclimatology, palaeoecology, and palaeoanthropology, with all entries referenced to their source publications. It is incomplete — particularly for the Lower Laetoli Beds, the Naibadad Beds, and the Ngaloba Beds — and will likely remain so. It is not a peer-reviewed work and should be treated accordingly: entries reflect the state of the literature as consulted during compilation and may not incorporate more recent findings. One potential stratigraphic ambiguity has been noted in the Olpiro Beds dating and is left for specialist assessment. Errors and further gaps are possible. The author welcomes corrections.

Bed	Tuff / Strata	Bayesian Age (Ma) [+/- 95% Conf. Int.]	K-Feldspar Age (Ma) ± 2σ MSE	Palaeoenvironment	Ecology	Lithic / Bone Artefacts	Human-like Fossils & Locality
		<small>[A.L. Deniro, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4] If no other specified</small>					
				<small>[T. Harrison & A. Kweka, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_2, Chapter 2] & [T. Harrison (ed.), 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9962-4_7]</small>			
							- Loc. 15 , fossils of Late Pleistocene age, in association with stone tools and ostrich egg shell beads (3°12'59.6"S, 35°08'51.5" E), found scattered on the surface (derived from the mbuga clays and river alluvium)
Ngaloba Beds >0.2 Ma	Upper Ngaloba Beds					- Loc. 2, (L.H. 18) Bone tools, points, projectile and cut marked bones suggest that humans started active hunting during the MSA period <small>[T. Mosuo & S. Kimambo, 2022, DOI: 10.1163/9789004500228_004, Chapter 2]</small>	- Loc. 2, MSA tools associated with faunal remains, & a relatively complete cranium of Homo cf. H. sapiens (L.H. 18) (Day et al., 1980; Magori & Day, 1983). Immediately postdates the trachytic tuff at Laetoli (Hay, 1987) <small>[T. Mosuo & S. Kimambo, 2022, DOI: 10.1163/9789004500228_004, Chapter 2]</small>
	- Upper Ngaloba trachytic tuff has been correlated to the lower Ndotu marker tuff at Oldupai (Day et al., 1980) <small>[T. Mosuo & S. Kimambo, 2022, DOI: 10.1163/9789004500228_004, Chapter 2]</small>	- Ndotu basal contact at 0.50 ± 0.04 Ma (95% confidence interval) <small>[A.L. Deniro et al., 2010, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990]</small> c. 129,000 ± 4,000 BP (U series) <small>[T. Mosuo & S. Kimambo, 2022, DOI: 10.1163/9789004500228_004, Chapter 2]</small>	40Ar/39Ar age for a tuff from 7.01 mbs slightly above the base of the Ndotu Bed (Oldupai Gorge) of 0.4788 ± 0.0043 Ma <small>[A.L. Deniro et al., 2010, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990]</small>				
	Lower Ngaloba Beds						
Olpiro Beds	Olpiro Marker Tuff		(2.070 ± 0.020 Ma)			- Loc. 16, large mammal fossils (although Leakey (1987a) suggests that most of these may originally have been derived from the Ngaloba Beds)	- Loc. 16, stone tools (although Leakey (1987a) suggests that most of these may originally have been derived from the Ngaloba Beds)
	Tuff below marker tuff		(2.057 ± 0.015 Ma)				
Naibadad Beds	Upper		2.057 ± 0.017 Ma				
	Middle		2.155 ± 0.012 Ma				
	Lower						
Upper Ndolanya Beds (UNB)			2.660 ± 0.016 Ma	- The UNB coincides with a major global climatic shift associated with increased intensification of northern hemisphere glaciation, and this likely led to greater aridity and the expansion of grasslands in eastern Africa <small>[T. Harrison, 2017, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-46646-0_4]</small> - The UNB was dominated by woodland and was not substantially different, at least in the general composition of the major vegetation types, from the ULB <small>[T. Harrison, 2017, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-46646-0_4]</small> - Reduced diversity of the browsing ungulates and the appearance of new species of equids and bovids that were more specialized for cursoriality and grazing (new species of <i>Eurygnathohippus</i> and of several new alcelaphins and antilopins). It is likely that there was a slight increase in aridity and the proportion of grassland <small>[T. Harrison, 2017, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-46646-0_4]</small> - The UNB palaeoenvironment was occupied by four taxa of dung beetles, four other taxa of coleopterans, and two taxa of bees. Some wasps may also be represented in the three units. The UNB show the lowest diversity and abundance <small>[J. F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/aps.12357]</small> - The UNB represent a more open environment than was present during deposition of the ULB. Wooded-bushed grassland represents 43.2% of the sample, followed by light woodland-bushland (29.5%) and heavy woodland-bushland (18.2%) with a minor forest component (4.5%) (based on a sample of 205 extant adult bovids + 360 fossil specimens analyzed from the ULB and 170 from the UNB) <small>[K. Kovarik & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18]</small>	- Loc. 7E , high percentage of postcranial remains of medium to large-sized bovids , including associated elements and partial skeletons (Leakey, 1987a) - Loc. 18 , fossil vertebrates are common in both units, consisting predominantly of bovids; Cocoons and brood cells of solitary hymenopterans - Loc. 22S , rich vertebrate fauna - The evidence suggests that <i>Paranthropus</i> occupied habitats at Laetoli that were not substantially different from those of <i>Australopithecus afarensis</i> earlier in time <small>[T. Harrison, 2017, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-46646-0_4]</small>		- Silal Artum, EP 1500/01 (maxilla), Paranthropus aethiopicus, 2.66 Ma <small>[A.L. Deniro, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4]</small> <i>P. aethiopicus</i> was adapted to a specialized diet of tougher, more fibrous plant matter <small>[K. Kovarik & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18]</small> - Loc. 7E, LAET 75–3817 (Rt zygomatic process of frontal; two associated bone frags. (infant)), cf. Hominini indet. - Loc. 22S, EP 1000/98 (proximal tibia of an adult individual), Paranthropus aethiopicus, 2.66 Ma <small>[A.L. Deniro, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4]</small> Bipedalism was firmly established <small>[K. Kovarik & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18]</small>
Lower Ndolanya Beds		3.58 [+0.023, – 0.026]	3.58 ± 0.03 Ma			- Loc. 23 , fossils vertebrates (large mammals)	- Loc. 23, Acheulian tools predominately made of calcrete, associated with well-preserved remains of large mammals
Upper Laetoli Beds (ULB)	YMT (Yellow Marker Tuff)	3.623 [+0.015, – 0.015]	3.627 ± 0.018 Ma (weighted mean age)			- Loc.1, fossil wood and root casts	
	- Accumulation of the entire ULB required less than 220 ka from emplacement of the uppermost aeolian tuff of the LLB, through the ULB inclusive of the Yellow Marker Tuff, corresponding			- We identify a trend during the 200 kyr deposition of the Upper Laetoli Beds, during which the proportion of woodland, bushland and grass-dominated habitat types shifts throughout the sequence . 39.7% is found in the heavy woodland-bushland category, followed by lower proportions in light woodland-bushland (17.4%) and wooded-bushed grassland (21.1%). A forest component is also represented (13.6%) (based on a sample of		- Loc. 16 , vertebrate fossils are all derived from between Tuffs 7 and the Yellow Marker Tuff	- Loc. 1, L.H. 15 (Lt M ₂), 0.9 m above Tuff 8 - Loc. 16, EP 2400/00 (mandibular fragment with P ₃ -M ₁), <i>Australopithecus afarensis</i> , found 51 cm above Tuff 8. Can be fairly tightly constrained stratigraphically to 0.5–1.3 m above Tuff 8

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		[A.L. Deniro, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4] If no other specified					[T. Harrison & A. Kweka, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_2, Chapter 2] & [T. Harrison (ed.), 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9962-4_7]	
to a minimum sedimentation rate of 22 cm/ka.		3.63 Ma (30 cm above Tuff 8)		205 extant adult bovids + 360 fossil specimens analyzed from the ULB and 170 from the UNB) [K. Kovarovic & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18] - There is a distinct difference in the faunas of the ULB and the UNB one million years later, both in terms of species composition (Su & Harrison 2007, 2008) and ecomorphology. There is some evidence for a shift in ecomorphology within the Upper Laetoli Beds [K. Kovarovic & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18]			Australopithecus afarensis specimens recovered from horizons throughout the ULB, ranging from between Tuff 1 to 30 cm above Tuff 8, are constrained to 3.85–3.63 Ma [A.L. Deniro, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4]	
	Tuff 8	3.634 [+0.017, – 0.013]	3.631 ± 0.018 Ma (inferred eruption age)	- The ULB ecosystem was composed predominantly of closed and open woodlands with large tracts of grassland [T. Harrison, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9962-4_7] - The ULB palaeoenvironment supported a larger number of taxa of termites, one species of dung beetle, eleven taxa of bees, and five other taxa of coleopterans. The ULB palaeoenvironments showed the greatest abundance of individuals based on the number of trace fossils recovered [J.F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/jpa.12357] - The full development of the <i>Celliforma</i> ichnofacies in the ULB indicates the dominance of a palaeoenvironment of shrubland to woodland with limited grass cover [J.F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/jpa.12357] - On the basis of habitat preferences of the antelopes recovered from Laetoli, there is evidence for the continuous regional presence of woodland and forest throughout deposition of the Upper Laetoli Beds. Antelopes preferring forest and heavy cover habitats dominate the assemblage. Antelopes that locomoted principally in open and light cover habitats are largely in the minority [J. C. Bishop et al., 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_17]	- Heavy woodland-bushland is the lowest (33.9%) above Tuff 7 (based on a sample of 205 extant adult bovids + 360 fossil specimens analyzed from the ULB and 170 from the UNB) [K. Kovarovic & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18] - Loc. 3 , fossiliferous horizon 60–70 cm above Tuff 7, maybe a small waterhole that flooded seasonally, at least 40 m wide, rich in fossil dung, twigs, seeds, and insects (see Bamford, 2011a; Krell & Schawaller, 2011; Kitching & Sadler, 2011; Harrison 2011a) - Loc. 10E , fossil vertebrates have been recovered from between Tuffs 7 and 8 - Loc.17 , some relatively rare taxa , such as <i>Paracolobus</i> and <i>Orycteropus</i> ; A tuffaceous horizon contains a dense aggregation of unbranched vertical burrows leading to brood cells of solitary hymenopterans , estimated density of over 2,000 burrows per m ²			
							- Loc. 1, L.H. 1 (Rt P ₄ frag), <i>A. afarensis</i> , ~1.2 m above Tuff 7 - Loc. 3, L.H. 2 (partial mandible of a juvenile individual), <i>A. afarensis</i> , from ~0.5 m above Tuff 7 - Loc. 7, L.H. 3 (partial upper and lower dentition), <i>A. afarensis</i> , between Tuffs 7 and 8, just above xenolith horizon, L.H. 6 (associated upper teeth), ~0.5 m above Tuff 7 - Loc. 11 (~0.9 m above Tuff 7), upper cheek teeth of a single individual of a hominin (L.H. 8 and L.H. 22), <i>A. afarensis</i> , found 2 years apart (Leakey, 1987b) - Loc. 16, EP 162/00 (left lower canine), of <i>A. afarensis</i> (Harrison, 2011b), found on the surface between Tuffs 7 and 8	- Loc. 7 , and L.H. 30 (Lt dC ¹) (Leakey, 1987b), probably between Tuffs 6 and 8 - Loc. 9, L.H. 17 (Lt M ¹), <i>A. afarensis</i> , between Tuffs 5 and 8
	Tuff 7A (Footprint Tuff)	3.66 Ma (new interpolated age) - In Loc. 1 , Tuff 7 lies 4 m below dated Tuff 8	3.66 ± 0.02 Ma (Biotite age) 3.55 ± 0.03 Ma (Hornblende age)	- Mammal, bird and insect prints and trails have been identified in 18 sites (labelled from A to R) out of 33 total palaeontological localities in the Laetoli area (Leakey, 1987a; Musiba et al., 2008; Harrison & Kweka, 2011) [T. M. Mosso et al., 2016, DOI: 10.7554/ol.10568] - Loc. 13, raindrop imprints are numerous at site L1 [C.M. Mkuubho et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1080/10420940802470383] 	- Loc. 4 , an abundance of calcified plant material, including leaves, twigs (up to 4 cm in diameter) and seeds, fossil thorns and impressions of compound microphyllous leaves, similar to those of <i>Acacia</i> - Loc. 7, footprint Site R , 1,799 prints (lagomorphs and Madoqua, ancient elephants, buffalos, giraffes, lions, baboons, rhinoceros, elands, gazelles, hartebeests, roan antelopes, guinea fowls and beetles. A number of indeterminate carnivore and bird) [C.M. Mkuubho et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1080/10420940802470383] - Loc. 8, footprint Site Q 28 prints (giraffe, roan antelope, gazelle, guinea fowl, rhino and buffalo) [C.M. Mkuubho et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1080/10420940802470383] - Loc. 11, footprint Sites D and E (elephantid, <i>Madoqua</i> , hyenas, and guinea fowl; Leakey, 1987c) [see header row] - Lagomorphs and Madoqua prints dominated the footprint assemblage at Locality D ; <i>Simatherium kohllarseni</i> , hartebeest, carnivore indet., Aves indet. [C.M. Mkuubho et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1080/10420940802470383] - Loc. 13, footprint Sites L1 and L2 ; rhinoceros prints predominate among those of the large animals (giraffes, roan antelopes, gazelles, guinea fowls, rhinoceroses, buffalos, elephants, baboons, hyenas, lions, oribi, hartebeests, elands, zebras and <i>Simatherium kohllarseni</i> ; rabbit and dik-dik prints were the most numerous) [C.M. Mkuubho et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1080/10420940802470383] - Loc. 21 , calcified plant material		- Loc. 2, Footprint sites O and P are located at the southern end (Leakey, 1987c) - Loc. 7 , hominin footprint Sites A, B, and C (Leakey, 1987c) - Loc. 8 , the hominin trail of footprints, presumably of <i>A. afarensis</i> (Sites G, S (c. 150 m to the south of Site G)) - Loc. 9, footprint Site K (Leakey, 1987c) - Loc. 10E, footprint sites (F, H, I, J) (Leakey, 1987c) - Loc. 13, footprint Sites L, M and N (Leakey, 1987c)	
	Lower Tuff 7 Base of Tuff 7				- Loc. 15 , numerous		- Loc. 2, L.H. 25 (an	

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							[F. Harrison & A. Kweks, 2011, DOI 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_2, Chapter 2] & [F. Harrison (ed.), 2011, DOI 10.1007/978-90-481-9962-4_7]	
					lagomorphs and rodents, a skull and partial skeleton of a new species of medium-size alcelaphine (Gentry, 2011); cocoons and brood cells of solitary hymenopterans are very common, especially in the upper part of the section			isolated P ₃), A. afarensis , 15 cm above Tuff 6 - Loc. 7, L.H. 4 (mandible), lectotype of A. afarensis , 1.2 m below Tuff 7 - Loc. 8, L.H. 5, L.H. 27 and L.H. 28 (same individual; Rt maxilla frag., Rt M ₃ , Rt M ₂), L.H. 13 , (Rt mandibular frag., edentulous with roots of M ₁ -M ₃), A. afarensis , ~1.8 m – ~2 m below Tuff 7 - Loc. 10E, L.H. 24 (P ₃), A. afarensis , ~2.1 m below Tuff 7 - Loc. 12E, L.H. 21 (partial skeleton), immature individual of A. afarensis (White, 1980; Leakey, 1987b; Kyauka, 1994)
	Tuff 6	3.70 Ma (new interpolated age)						
								- Loc. 6, L.H. 16 (Rt M ₁), A. afarensis , just below Tuff 6 - Loc. 5, L.H. 7 (Rt M ₃), A. afarensis , ~0.6 m above Tuff 5 - Loc. 8, L.H. 19 (Lt M ₂), A. afarensis , between Tuffs 5 and 6 - Loc. 19, L.H. 14 , (partial lower dentition), A. afarensis , ~0.3 m above Tuff 5
	Tuff 5	3.79 Ma (new interpolated age)						
					- Loc. 13 , a partial skeleton of a large viper with an immature <i>Serengetilagus</i> skeleton preserved in its abdominal cavity (Rage & Bailon, 2011); majority of the fossils are derived from the Upper Laetoli Beds between Tuffs 5 and 8, but a few from between Tuffs 3 and 5			
	Tuff between 4 & 5	3.79 Ma (new interpolated age)						
								- Loc. 8, L.H. 29, A. afarensis (Harrison, 2011b), mandibular fragment, found on the surface in the lower part of the sequence (between Tuffs 4 and Yellow marker Tuff)
	Tuff 4	3.79 [+0.029, – 0.033] Ma	3.81 ± 0.04 Ma					
					- Loc. 10 , Tuff 3, which also forms the upper lip of a waterfall, about 5 m high , at the eastern boundary of the locality			- Loc. 5, L.H. 12 (Lt M ₃), 1.8 m below Tuff 4
	Tuff 3	3.80 Ma (new interpolated age)			- Loc. 5 , Tuff 3 is extensively exposed, and it preserves numerous footprints , especially those of guinea fowl and small mammals - Loc. 22E , the upper part of the tuff preserves a rich concentration of calcified plant remains (e.g., mats of fine roots), possibly of grasses; In one location (3°14'30"S, 35°11'52"E) Tuff 3 preserves numerous footprints , especially those of guinea fowl and small mammals			
	Base of Tuff 3				- Loc. 9 , calcified plant material is associated with the base of Tuff 3			
					- Loc. 9 , several small ovoid termitaries have been observed <i>in situ</i> below Tuff 3	- Heavy woodland-bushland is the highest (46.8%) below Tuff 3 (based on a sample of 205 extant adult bovids + 360 fossil specimens analyzed from the ULB and 170 from the UNB) [C. Kovarovic & P. Andrews, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_18]		
	Tuff 2	3.81 [+0.028, – 0.035] Ma	3.79 ± 0.04 Ma					
					- Loc. 9S , fossil vertebrates are quite common, as are relatively large termitaries (70–100 cm in diameter) - Loc. 10W , fossil termitaries are especially common at this locality (Darlington, 2011)			- Loc. 10W, L.H. 11, Australopithecus afarensis between Tuffs 1 and 2 [A.L. Dembo, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4] L.H. 10 (Lt mandibular frag., edentulous with broken roots C-M ₁), from below Tuff 2 (Leakey, 1987b)
	Tuff 1	3.83 Ma (new interpolated age)	(3.93 ± 0.06 Ma)					

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		<small>[A.L. Deino, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4] If no other specified</small>					<small>[F. Harrison & A. Kweks, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_2, Chapter 2] & [F. Harrison (ed.), 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9962-4_7]</small>
					- Loc. 10 , exceptionally well-preserved eggs of ground nesting birds (<i>Harrison, 2005</i>); Large termitaries and gastropods are common (see <i>Darlington, 2011; Tattersfield, 2011</i>); Most of the fossils are derived from between Tuff 2 and the bottom of the section		
Lower Laetoli Beds (LLB) - LLB unconformably overlies the Precambrian granitic basement at Kakesio	Uppermost part	3.85 [+0.021, - 0.017] Ma	3.85 ± 0.02 Ma (the age of a yellow, massive eolian tuff ~9 m thick, with ca. 5% phenocrysts of augite, biotite and anorthoclase (sample 1-LLB1) just below the contact with the ULB at Loc. 1)	- The LLB palaeoenvironment was inhabited at least by one species of moth, three taxa of dung beetles and five other taxa of coleopterans, nine taxa of bees, and an indeterminate number of taxa of termites <small>[J.F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/pole.12357]</small> - At Noiti and Esere, south of Laetoli, the LLB is dominated by fluvial, deltaic, and lacustrine deposits interbedded with air-fall tuffs and lahars <small>[J.F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/pole.12357]</small> - The LLB show only one-third of the abundance of specimens from ULB. The relative scarcity of <i>Coprinisphaera</i> suggest that the scarcity of fresh grasses and the low incidence of large grazers were the primary causes. The presence of a greater number of <i>Coprinisphaera</i> suggest a potential displacement from the <i>Celliforma</i> to the <i>Coprinisphaera</i> lchnofacies indicative of habitats with more extensive grass cover <small>[J.F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/pole.12357]</small>	- Kakesio 6 , most common fossils in the upper part of the section are small ovoid termitaries (Φ 30–50 cm), bee brood cells and cocoons, terrestrial gastropods, tortoises, and ostrich egg shell fragments; Terrestrial gastropods dominated by <i>Limicolaria</i> and <i>Achatina</i>		
	Upper part						
	Lower part						
	Lowermost part	- To the southwest of Laetoli, the base of the LLB deposited in a low-energy fluvial or paludal environment <small>[J.F. Genise & T. Harrison, 2018, DOI: 10.1111/pole.12357]</small>		4.36 ± 0.10 Ma (interpreted as an eruption age , with a weighted mean of the oldest tuff)	- Emboremony 2 , large mammals , small ovoid termitaria are common - Lobileita , the bottom half of the section has yielded fossil vertebrates, ostrich egg shell fragments, terrestrial gastropods, termitaries and traces of solitary bees	- Kakesio 6 , <i>Anancus</i> , <i>Ceratotherium</i> , bovids and equids; Fossil vertebrates are found throughout the section, appear to be most abundant in the lowermost 5 m ; Partial skeletons of <i>Parahyaena howelli</i> and aff. <i>Proteles</i> sp. (Werdelin & Dehghani, 2011); Calcified wood and root casts (Φ 2–5) are abundant in some levels. Kakesio is the only locality that has yielded large aquatic vertebrates (i.e., crocodiles), and supports evidence from the geology that fluvial sediments at the base of the Lower Laetoli Beds were associated with permanent or seasonal bodies of water (probably a shallow swampy depression with ephemeral streams, but not a major river or lake system). - Esere 2 , <i>Sanders (2011)</i> suggests that the <i>Anancus (kenyensis)</i> specimens from Endolele are more primitive than those from Kakesio, implying that the Lower Laetoli Beds at Esere might be somewhat older than those at Kakesio - Noiti 1 , the fossil wood and lahar are inferred to be contemporaneous with the Lower Laetoli Beds	
- Previously published K–Ar and 40Ar/39Ar dates quoted in this manuscript have been adjusted upward for consistency with a reference age of 28.201 Ma for the Fish Canyon sanidine (<i>Kuiper et al., 2008</i>), the irradiation monitor mineral used in this study. For the conventional K–Ar ages of <i>Drake and Curtis (1987)</i> and <i>Leakey et al. (1976)</i> , this conversion results in an increase of ~0.6% from the published ages. For the previously published 40Ar/39Ar ages, the following conversions apply: <i>Manega (1993)</i> , 1.26%; <i>Ndessokia (1990)</i> , 1.26%; <i>Mollet et al. (2011)</i> , 0.65%; <i>McDougall and Brown (2008)</i> , 0.36%. Also, prior results are herein quoted at 2σ analytical error <small>[A.L. Deino, 2011, DOI: 10.1007/978-90-481-9956-3_4]</small> .							- (Loc. 8, footprint sites G and S) The two individuals S1 and S2 were taller and had a larger body mass than the G individuals. The estimated about 165 cm stature of S1 is quite remarkable, exceeding G2 by more than 20 cm. The new estimates for the Laetoli individuals indicate an even more marked variation in body size within the same hominin population, at 3.66 Ma. The combined records from Laetoli and Hadar suggest that large-bodied hominins existed in the African Pliocene for over 400,000 years, between 3.66 and 3.2 Ma. The record of bipedal tracks from Laetoli Loc. 8 envisage a scenario in which at least five individuals (G1, G2, G3, S1 and S2) were walking in the same time frame, in the same direction and at a similar moderate speed. This aspect must be evaluated in association with the pronounced body-size variation within the sample, which implies marked differences between age ranges and a considerable degree of sexual dimorphism in <i>Au. afarensis</i> <small>[F.T. Masao et al., 2016, DOI: 10.7554/eLife.19568]</small> .